

European Swine Influenza Network Report #3 on Swine Influenza A Viruses Evolution and Diversity in Europe from October 2024 to September 2025

Gautier RICHARD¹, Pia RYT-HANSEN², Alexander M. P. BYRNE³, European Swine Influenza Network.

¹ French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety (ANSES), Ploufragan-Plouzané-Niort Laboratory, Swine Virology Innovation and Genomics Unit, National Reference Laboratory for Swine Influenza, BP53, 22440 Ploufragan, France.

² Dpt. of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, University of Copenhagen, Grønnegårdsvej 2, DK-1870 Frederiksberg C, Denmark.

³ Worldwide Influenza Centre, The Francis Crick Institute, 1 Midland Road, London NW1 1AT, United Kingdom.

Introduction

Swine Influenza A viruses (swIAV) are highly prevalent among pigs in Europe and pose a significant threat to public health due to their potential spillover to humans and subsequent pandemic potential. The intensification of pig production systems and the unrestricted movement of live swine promote the spread of swIAV in Europe across national borders. Systematic surveillance of swIAV evolution in Europe plays a crucial role in early detection of potential zoonotic or pandemic strains, facilitates informed decision-making in vaccine candidate selection and enhances overall public and animal health preparedness.

Recognizing the importance of coordinated efforts, the European Swine Influenza Network (ESFLU) has been established as a COST Action scientific network. Its primary objective is to foster scientific collaboration and enhance capacity at the European level for monitoring the evolution and spread of swIAVs, as well as identifying measures to prevent the spread of swIAVs within and between European countries. A pivotal component of ESFLU activities is the task undertaken by Working Group (WG) 2, which involves the annual compilation of a report detailing the evolution of swIAVs across Europe. This report is a result of collaborative efforts with ESFLU WG2 members sharing swIAV sequences derived from field samples collected and sequenced between October 2022 and September 2025. To achieve this, rigorous phylogenetic analyses were conducted on the compiled sequences, and the results were made available online through a Nextstrain instance (<https://nextstrain.org/groups/esflu>). These analyses sought to determine the diversity of swIAVs in specific countries and their respective proportions based on the classification and analysis of all eight influenza A virus (IAV) segments. Moreover, the analyses aimed to ascertain whether specific viruses had potentially traversed national boundaries, indicating the cross-border movement of these viruses, or shared evolutionary history of viruses with the same genotype and closely related genes in several countries.

ESFLU WG2 also provides a crucial connection between ESFLU and OFFLU; the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH) / Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations (FAO) network of expertise on animal influenza. OFFLU performs bi-annual analyses of swIAVs circulating globally, with the aim of identifying contemporary swIAVs to support the designation of candidate vaccine viruses for pandemic preparedness (<https://www.offlu.org/index.php/offlu-vcm-summary-reports/>). As part of this activity, WG2 assists in the sharing of swIAV sequences between ESFLU members and OFFLU to facilitate increased resolution of swIAV diversity within ESFLU member countries. As such, this will help increase the output and visibility of ESFLU at the international level. Regular updates of this nature are paramount for staying ahead of potential public and animal health threats. By continuously monitoring swIAV evolution in Europe, ESFLU

WG2 reports endeavor to provide timely information to support enhanced preparedness of public health systems at the European level concerning swIAVs.

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Methods

The collected sequences were checked for their quality by removing sequences with more than 16 undetermined nucleotides (N) using ``seqkit grep -s -r -i -v -p [ATGC][ATGC][ATGC][ATGC]NNNNNNN.*NNNNNNN[ATGC][ATGC][ATGC][ATGC]``. Sequences that were too short were also removed by using ``seqkit seq -u -g -m X``, with X replaced as the following values for each segment: PB2 = 1617, PB1 = 1592, PA = 1517, HA = 1191, NP = 1076, NA = 987, MP = 687, NS = 590 (Shen et al., 2016). All segments clades were labelled using the influenza sequences toolbox (Richard et al., 2025a; Richard, 2026) genotypeFasta tool using a modified version of the OctoFlu database (Anderson et al., 2022) available on the influenza sequences toolbox repository, with appropriate M pdm, NP pdm and H1C.2.4.3 identification for swIAVs. Sequences were aligned separately using ``mafft --auto`` (Katoh and Standley, 2013). Maximum-likelihood and time-scaled phylogenies were computed for all segments using the Nextstrain auspice pipeline (Hadfield et al., 2018) based on IQTREE2 (Minh et al., 2020) and TreeTime (Sagulenko et al., 2018).

Results

A total of 718 swIAV strains with at least an HA and an NA sequence have been collected in Europe between October 1st 2024 and September 30th 2025 within 16 countries, of which 653 have been collected within ESFLU, and 65 additional sequences were collected from the GISAID platform based on their submission dates following the same period (EPI_SET_260311mg, doi.org/10.55876/gis8.260311mg). In total, 523 (72.8%) strains were sequenced at the full genome level. All strains have been genotyped at least on the HA and NA segments (Figure 1) and on the internal genes when available. HA/NA clades were categorized within HA/NA lineages (H1A, H1B, H1C, H3.1970, H3.2000, H3.2010, H3.2020, N1EA, N1P, N2EU, N2G, N2HS, N2S) (Anderson et al., 2016; Hufnagel et al., 2023; Zeller et al., 2021). Among the 718 strains, 717 had an HA and NA sequence of sufficient quality to be analyzed phylogenetically. They displayed a preferential pairing between HA and NA clades (Figure 1, with an interactive version available at: <https://nextstrain.org/groups/ESFLU/ESFLU-10-2022-09-2025/HA:groups/ESFLU/ESFLU-10-2022-09-2025/NA>), which is analysed per country at different diversity levels throughout the report below. The sporadicity of the H1B and H3 lineages at the European level was visible compared to the H1A and H1C lineages.

Figure 1: HA (left) NA (right) tanglegram of 717 swIAVs strains collected between 01-10-2024 and 30-09-2025 in Europe among 16 countries. The phylogenies are colored by their respective clades, and the lines linking the HA and NA sequences of a given strain are colored following swIAV lineages.

SwIAV lineages distribution has been analysed for each country displaying at least 2 sequences for the considered period (Table 1, two countries of the 16 countries were filtered out since they had only one sequence). It is clear that the H1A/N1P (previously H1pdmN1pdm), H1C/N1EA (previously H1avN1av), and H1C/N2G (previously H1avN2) were the most widespread lineages, being present in 12, 11 and 10 of the 14 analysed countries, respectively. The number of different lineages identified in each country is correlated to the number of submitted sequences, with between six and seven lineages found in Belgium, Denmark, France, Germany, Italy and The Netherlands. Spain and Italy had quite a diverse panel of swIAV lineages representing 11 and 10 different swIAV HA and NA lineages combinations. Belgium, France, Germany, Italy, the UK and Switzerland all had a relatively high number of detections of H1C/N1EA, whereas H1C/N2G was detected in high numbers in Denmark, France, Germany, Italy, The Netherlands and Poland. H1A/N2G was detected more sporadically but across seven different countries. The H1A/N1EA and H1B/N2G were both detected in five countries, with H1A/N1EA especially being observed in high numbers in Denmark. Ten lineages were found to be country-specific, mainly representing H3 lineages. Interestingly, H3.2020/N2HS representing human seasonal HA and NA segments were detected in both France and the Russian Federation. These segments were similar to contemporary H3N2 IAVs circulating in humans and thus highlight cases of potentially recent reverse zoonoses.

Table 1: Spatial distribution of swIAVs lineages collected between 01-10-2024 and 30-09-2025 in Europe.

Lineage	Austria	Belgium	Denmark	France	Germany	Italy	Netherlands	Northern Ireland	Poland	Russian Federation	Spain	Sweden	Switzerland	United Kingdom	Total Countries
H1A/N1EA	0	0	34	12	4	9	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	5
H1A/N1P	2	0	10	28	4	8	1	6	1	3	3	6	0	3	12
H1A/N2EU	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1A/N2G	0	3	8	7	7	3	6	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	7
H1B/N1EA	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
H1B/N2EU	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1B/N2G	2	4	0	0	7	0	6	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	5
H1B/N2S	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	5	3
H1C/N1EA	5	23	9	82	30	36	21	0	0	2	6	0	14	7	11
H1C/N1P	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1C/N2EU	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1C/N2G	0	3	85	71	16	21	7	0	5	2	5	4	0	0	10
H1C/N2S	0	2	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	3
H3.2000/N1EA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
H3.2000/N2G	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	1
H3.2000/N2S	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	1
H3.2010/N2EU	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H3.2010/N2G	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H3.2020/N2G	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H3.2020/N2HS	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	2
#Lineages/country	3	6	7	7	6	10	6	2	2	4	11	2	1	3	0

HA/NA clades have been analysed per country and displayed over 2-week periods (fortnight distributions) for the considered period between 01-10-2024 and 30-09-2025 (Figure 2). This visualisation highlights the need for improved surveillance within Europe despite the lack of a notifiable disease status for swIAVs, as there were huge differences in the number of samples and distribution of subtypes over time per country. Moreover, each country displayed specific combinations of swIAV HA/NA clades over the considered period, with Italy, Spain and Denmark displaying the highest diversity with 18, 18 and 16 HA/NA clade combinations, respectively. Despite a lower sampling, Germany displayed a higher diversity than France, with 13 versus 9 HA/NA clade combinations. Proportions of HA/NA clade combinations in each country were reported for three periods: 01-10-2022 to 30-09-2025, 01-10-2023 to 30-09-2024 and 01-10-2024 to 30-09-2025 (Figure 3). Between the 2023-2024 and 2024-2025 periods the proportions remained rather stable for each country. However, there were notable differences in France and Italy where instances of new combinations were observed - H1A.3.3.2/N1EA and H1A.3.3.2/N2G.2 - in France, and much less reported H1C.2.1/N1EA and H1C.2.2/N2G.2 in Italy, in 2024-2025 compared to 2023-2024.

Figure 2: Fortnightly distribution (2-week periods) of swIAVs combined HA clade and NA clade between 01-10-2024 and 30-09-2025 per country.

Figure 3: swIAV HA/NA clades combinations proportions based on sequenced strains per country between (A) 01-10-2022 and 30-09-2025, (B) 01-10-2023 and 30-09-2024, (C) 01-10-2024 and 30-09-2025.

At the full genome level, the genotypes of the 523 strains collected between 01-10-2024 and 30-09-2025 are represented in Table 2. As a reminder, the genotypes of the strains collected during the previous period between 01-10-2023 to 30-09-2024 are represented in Table 3. Internal genes were classified as follows: P for pdm09 clade, E for Eurasian avian-like clade and H for human seasonal 2020 clade. The previously labelled N2LAIV98 clade found in ESFLU Report 2 (Richard et al., 2025b) was changed to N2EU, since the corresponding sequences were related to 1995-1996 spillovers from human to swine which happened in Europe, rather than to the Texas 1998 live attenuated vaccine. In total, 75 genotypes were identified between 01-10-2024 and 30-09-2025, representing a significant increase compared to the 53 genotypes identified between 01-10-2023 and 30-09-2024. Most genotypes (n=50) were only detected sporadically, often two times or more, in a single country, indicating that these new genotypes are generated independently within a country. For the considered period, and similarly to the previous period, the genotypes H1C.2.2/N1EA/EEEEEE, the reassortant H1C.2.2/N1EA/EEEEPE and H1A.3.3.2/N1P/PPPPPP were the most widespread genotypes found in eight, seven and seven countries, respectively. H1C.2.2/N1EA/EEEEPE was the most predominant genotype found in Austria, Belgium and The Netherlands, H1C.2.2/N1EA/EEEEEE was the most predominant in Italy, The Netherlands and Switzerland, while the H1A.3.3.2/N1P/PPPPPP genotype was the most predominant only in Sweden. This was followed by the H1C.2.4.1/N2G.2/PPPPPP genotype, which was found in five countries (Denmark, Italy, Russian Federation, Spain, Sweden), which is an increase compared to the previous period, where it was only found in three countries (Denmark, Germany and Italy). H1A.3.3.2/N2G.2/PPPPPP, H1C.2.1/N1EA/EEEEEE and H1B.1.2.1/N2G.2/EEEEEE were the fourth most widespread swIAV genotypes in Europe, observed in four countries each, and these genotypes were also among the most widespread genotypes in the previous 2023-2024 period (found in five, four and three countries, respectively). H1C.2.1/N1EA/EEEEEE was the most predominant genotype found in France, but remained sporadic in proportion to other genotypes in other countries. In total, 16 different genotypes were found in at least two countries, including reassortants on the internal genes, highlighting potential co-evolution or shared evolution related to trade of infected animals between countries.

Conclusions

This report highlights the significant progress made by the ESFLU network and Working Group 2 in monitoring the evolution and diversity of swIAVs across Europe between October 2022 and September 2025, with a focus on the comparison between the 2024-2025 and 2023-2024 periods. Interactive versions of most graphics are made available online for participants and users to explore the swIAV diversity within a spatiotemporal context for all data cumulated within the ESFLU Network between 09-2022 and 09-2025 at the ESFLU Nextstrain public group: <https://nextstrain.org/groups/esflu>.

Table 2: Genotypes of swIAVs circulating in Europe between 01-10-2024 and 30-09-2025.

HA	NA	PB2	PB1	PA	NP	M	NS	Austria	Belgium	Denmark	Finland	France	Germany	Italy	Netherlands	Northern Ireland	Russian Federation	Spain	Sweden	Switzerland	United Kingdom	Total Countries
H1A.3.3.2	N1EA	P	E	P	P	P	P	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
H1A.3.3.2	N1EA	P	P	P	P	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
H1A.3.3.2	N1EA	P	P	P	P	P	E	0	0	16	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
H1A.3.3.2	N1EA	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	4	0	10	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
H1A.3.3.2	N1P	P	P	P	P	P	E	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1A.3.3.2	N1P	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	5	0	24	0	7	0	5	2	3	6	0	0	7
H1A.3.3.2	N2EU4	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1A.3.3.2	N2G.2	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1A.3.3.2	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	1
H1A.3.3.2	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	E	P	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1A.3.3.2	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	E	0	0	3	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	3
H1A.3.3.2	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	3	4	0	7	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
H1B.1.1.1	N2S	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
H1B.1.1	N2EU	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1B.1.2.1	N1EA	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1B.1.2.1	N2G.2	E	E	E	E	E	E	2	2	0	0	0	3	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
H1B.1.2.1	N2S	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
H1B.1.2.1	N2S	E	E	E	E	P	E	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1B.1.2.2	N1EA	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1B.1.2	N2G.2	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	1
H1B.1.2	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	1
H1B.1.2	N2S	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
H1C.2.1	N1EA	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	63	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	4
H1C.2.1	N1EA	E	E	E	E	P	E	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2
H1C.2.1	N1EA	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	1
H1C.2.1	N2G.1	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
H1C.2.1	N2S	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
H1C.2.2	N1EA	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	2	4	0	4	1	26	3	0	0	1	0	12	0	8
H1C.2.2	N1EA	E	E	E	E	P	E	5	15	3	0	4	3	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	7
H1C.2.2	N1EA	P	P	P	E	P	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
H1C.2.2	N1EA	P	P	P	P	E	P	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	1
H1C.2.2	N1EA	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1C.2.2	N2G.1	E	E	E	E	P	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1C.2.2	N2G.2	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
H1C.2.2	N2G.2	E	E	E	E	P	E	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2
H1C.2.2	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	E	0	0	5	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
H1C.2.4.1	N1EA	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1C.2.4.1	N2G.1	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	9	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
H1C.2.4.1	N2G.2	E	E	E	P	E	E	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1C.2.4.1	N2G.2	P	E	P	P	P	P	0	0	5	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
H1C.2.4.1	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	E	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
H1C.2.4.1	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	12	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	3	1	0	0	5
H1C.2.4.1	N2S	E	E	E	E	P	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
H1C.2.4.2	N1EA	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1C.2.4.2	N1EA	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1C.2.4.2	N2G.2	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	1	0	49	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
H1C.2.4.2	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	E	0	0	1	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
H1C.2.4.2	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
H1C.2.4.3	N1P	P	P	P	P	P	E	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1C.2.4.3	N2EU4	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1C.2.4.3	N2G.1	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1C.2.4.3	N2G.2	P	E	E	P	P	E	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1C.2.4.3	N2G.2	P	E	P	P	P	P	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
H1C.2.4.3	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	E	0	0	14	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
H1C.2.4.3	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	5	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
H1C.2.4	N1EA	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1C.2.4	N2G.2	E	P	P	P	P	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1C.2.4	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	E	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1C.2.5	N2EU4	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1C.2.5	N2G.1	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1C.2.5	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	E	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H1C.2.5	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	2
H1C.2.6	N1EA	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	1
H3.2000.3	N1EA	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
H3.2000.3	N2G.1	E	E	E	E	P	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
H3.2000.3	N2G.2	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	1
H3.2000.3	N2G.2	P	P	P	P	P	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	1
H3.2000.3	N2S	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	1
H3.2000.3	N2S	E	E	E	E	P	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	1
H3.OH-2010	N2EU4	E	E	E	E	E	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H3.OH-2010	N2G.1	P	P	P	P	P	E	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H3.OH-2020	N2G.1	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H3.OH-2020	N2HS	H	H	H	H	H	H	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
H3.OH-2020	N2HS	P	P	P	P	P	P	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	1

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